

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D1.1

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from [01/01/2023] to [30/09/2023]
Periodic report date and version:	[30/09/2023]
Task 1.1 Leader	Prof. Mario Tribaudino (Unito)
D1.1 Responsible	POLITO

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.

Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.
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A) Main objectives achieved

- The main objectives of this RM are the Collection of data, processing technologies and waste characterization.
- The primary objective for the first reporting period (D1.1) was the collection of data related to waste characterization and processing technologies for both mineral and organic waste.
- This critical task involved gathering comprehensive information on innovative methods and established practices for the efficient and sustainable management of these waste streams. This initial phase sets the foundation for the development of the project in the next stages.
- During these first 10 months of project the task 1.1 (collection of data , processing technologies and waste characterization) has been completed(and in particular the main results achieved are:
 - Comprehensive review of the literature (and identification of fields of application)
 - Development of a syllabus/database of mineral and organic waste objects of the RM1

Table - List of Deliverables (M1: January 2023)

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL**	DUE DATE
D1.1	Collection of data, processing technologies	R	A database and a report on collected information (production, characteristics, and localisation data, together with representative processing technologies).	POLITO	PU	M9
D1.2	Characterization of waste and new products from Mineral and bio-organic waste.	DB	A database reporting the characteristics of the investigated mineral and organic waste and (recycled) products obtained after treatment activities (described in T1.3) will be delivered. Together with it, an operative manual to populate and fill the database will be also produced.	UNITO	PU	M22
D1.3	Treatment and processing activities for mineral and bio-organic waste	R	A report on the investigated treatment activities (methodologies, procedures, limits, etc.) will be produced.	UNITO	PU	M24
D1.4	Pilot Sites Recycled Products Application	R	Pilot sites to test and validate the proposed technologies will be assessed	UNITO	PU	M32

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
MS1.1	Treatment Activities for EQW, CDW, EW	1	12	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.2	Data collection and processing of EQW, CDW, EW, CW	1	12	Collection of data and processing info for LCA within the due date (LCA linked to RM6)
MS1.3	Pilot Sites testing activities	1	18	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.4	Recycled Products Application (from MW/OBW)	1	24	Planning and authorisation delivered

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Research Module n.1	Start month: 1	End month: 9						
Title: Circular waste, processing of Mineral and Organic Biowaste								
Location in Mezzogiorno: N								
Leader:	UNITO							
Partners involved:	POLITO	UPO						
Type of action	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months	130							

Output and results:

Activities:

1. Literature review

A literature review on the theoretical framework and current applications of mineral (Construction and Demolition Waste - CDW, including excavation waste - EW; extractive waste from quarrying activities – EWQ; ceramic materials waste – CMW; municipal solid waste from incinerators MSWI) and Organic Bio-Waste (OBW), have been carried out to provide an overview of waste management and resource utilization.

By meticulously reading and mapping articles within the main cluster of interest, this review synthesizes and provides an overview of current development, highlighting key trends and advancements.

The literature review focused on different clusters of research areas and topics to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in handling mineral and organic waste.

The following are the main research clusters identified by the working group (in part carried out during T1.1 Activities, and in part individuated to be developed in the following tasks):

- **Waste Characterization,**
- **Environmental Impact Assessment**

- Waste Management and Disposal Practices
- Reclamation and Remediation.
- Regulations and Compliance
- Recycling and Resource Recovery
- Case Studies and Best Practices
- Innovation and Emerging Technologies

The research was conducted on Scopus and Web of science Database in order to provide an overview of the state of the art at the national and international level. Each research team had a different field of research and focus of interest.

Detailed description of fields of investigation and teams (7 in total) is as in the following.

A. The research team led by Giovanna. A. Dino, Francesca Gambino, Manuela Lasagna, Domenico Antonio De Luca and Sabrina Bonetto (Earth Sciences Department - UNITO), Marco Casale (Management Department – UNITO), Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Dept. of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Science, UNITO), Giuseppina Cerrato and Alessia Giordana (Dept. of Chemistry, UNITO), Claudio Oggieri and Rossana Bellopede (DITAG – POLITO) focused on extractive waste (EW) and construction and demolition waste (CDW).

The products derived from the treatment of mining and quarry wastes (namely Extractive Waste) can vary on the basis of the materials being extracted and the industrial treatment they receive. Those products from industrial treatment cycles can be used for several aims.

1. **Quarry waste (QW)** can be categorized into different types based on their composition and characteristics. QW can be divided in different categories such as, i.e., overburden, soil, waste rock, coarse waste coming from working plants, residual sludge. A particular attention was given to quarry waste from the extraction of **marble, limestone, granite, gneiss, and aggregates**. For each of these categories has been developed a literature analysis that explores the characterisation of waste on the basis of specific geological setting, minero-petrographic, geochemical, physical and geotechnical characteristics. Treatment and processing at lab. and pilot plants scales, together with most interesting and promising “recycled” products are also available from literature. **Main objectives are:**
 - the investigation of potential recovery of CRM (critical raw materials) from siliceous waste rocks (a study at Piedmont level is in progress)
 - the exploitation of both coarse and fine fractions for the production of restoration mortars (as aggregate and for the production of lime);
 - the development of sustainable and safe horse footing areas, using technosol produced using mineral waste and organic compound, together with selected fraction (sand dimension) as sublayers. The structure of arena surface is characterized by three layers: top - base - sub-base. Technical criteria of impact firmness, cushioning, responsiveness, grip and uniformity need to be respected in order to safeguard the health of the musculoskeletal structures of the horse. Moreover, the health of both animals and stakeholders in terms of respirable airborne particles (e.g. silica) and the water holding capacity of the riding surfaces should be taken into account.

2. Mining waste (MW) can vary significantly based on the type of mining operation and the materials being extracted. The literature review provides an overview of the different categories for various types of mines. Main waste connected to mining activities are: waste rocks, operating residues and tailings (some of these waste can be intended as hazardous waste and others as inert waste). Literature has been organized in three different categories, depending on the original mines: **Precious Metals Extractive Waste, Other Metals Extractive Waste, Industrial Minerals Extractive Waste.**

Main objectives are:

- the evaluation of the potential resources arising from EW facilities in terms of RM, CRM and SRM.
- the investigation of potential recovery of CRM (critical raw materials) from historical and active mining sites and contemporary exploitation of by-products coming from the processing of mining waste.

3. Construction and demolition waste (CDW, including excavation waste). Construction and Demolition waste represent the first source of waste production at EU level (35% of total waste production). A literature review about origin and production of CDW (including excavation waste) has been carried out, focusing on treatment processing, best practices and protocols for their application. **Main objectives are the investigation of potential recovery of:**

- fine fraction for technosol production for environmental purposes and for horse footing arenas.
- coarse fraction for civil and infrastructure applications, together with sublayers for horse footing arenas
- selected materials to use as "aggregates" for the restoration mortars.

B. The research team, composed by Marco Bruno, Cesare Comina, Chiara Groppo, Anna Maria Ferrero, Stefano Ghignone, Andrea Giuliani, Franco Rolfo, Linda Pastero, Sergio Vinciguerra, Gessica Umili, and Dr Battista Taboni, (DST - UNITO), Maria Rita Migliazza, Maria Teresa Carriero (DISEG - POLITO), Federico Vagnon, Marilena Cardu (DIATI - POLITO)

Quarry waste: the present team focuses on carbonatic waste rocks. Carbonatic rocks are exploited for several industrial applications and as ornamental stones such as marble which requires a peculiar mining method based on the extraction of interigerand dimensioned blocks. This procedure is only possible in portions of the rock masses with a low fracturing degree, causing otherwise a high production of waste. There are several possible reuse applications of this waste material connected to its petrographic and mineralogical features as well as to its physical mechanical properties in short and long terms. The tendency to alteration of carbonate rocks in peculiar environmental conditions can be a strong limitation in their utilization and this problem is still a matter of detailed studies among the scientific community in cooperation with mining industries and construction companies.

Mine waste: Exploitation of natural resources is fundamental in our society, especially for strategic elements (REE, lithium, boron...). The extraction activities produce, as waste, huge amounts of material that is usually thought as useless. The storage and/or re-use of such waste materials is a problem, often difficult to handle especially for those exploitations that present peculiar logistic limitations (e.g., high altitude, proximity to natural reserves, extreme climate variation through seasons...). An accurate and detailed characterization of waste material through minero-petrographic investigations (e.g., XRD,

Raman, XRF, SEM-EDS) and geotechnical and geophysical tests provides fundamental information on its nature. Chemical-physical and mechanical properties will be used for driving the exploitation, reducing the amount of waste material processed during enrichment and concentration phases. Though an *in-situ* partial concentration, exploitation will implement productivity, reducing costs in terms of funding and environmental pollution.

Main objectives are:

- the investigation of quarry and mining area in order to reduce waste production by means of both advanced classification and modeling systems of the exploitations and onsite treatments.
- the study of the alteration of carbonatic rocks to evaluate the further potential use of carbonatic waste in the building sector taking pollutants action into account.

C. The research team led by Prof. Mario Tribaudino and Dr. Andrea Bernasconi (Dip. Scienze della Terra, UNITO) developed the literature review on bottom ashes, fly ashes and fired ceramic waste.

1. Bottom ashes from waste-to-energy (WTE) plants, which are also known as incinerator bottom ash (IBA), are the residues left behind after the combustion of municipal solid waste (MSW) and special non-hazardous waste. These ashes are typically the heavier, non-combustible materials that remain once the organic and combustible components of the waste have been burned off.

Primarily are composed of inorganic materials, including metals, glass, ceramics, and minerals. Proper disposal and management of bottom ashes are critical to prevent groundwater contamination and air pollution.

2. Fly ash are a fine, powdery by product that results from the combustion of pulverized coal in coal-fired power plants. Fly ash composition primarily consists of tiny, spherical particles composed of silicon dioxide (SiO_2), aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3), iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), and calcium oxide (CaO). It may also contain trace amounts of heavy metals, depending on the source of the coal.

At present bottom and fly ashes are recovered as a supplementary cementitious material in the construction industry to enhance the properties of concrete and in **road surfaces (not in Italy), 23.51 23.69 42.1**

3. Fired ceramic waste is generated during the production, use, or disposal of ceramics that have been fired at high temperatures (around 1200°C) to achieve their final form. The composition of fired ceramic waste varies depending on its source. It primarily consists of fired ceramic body (glass and crystalline phases), but it may also contain glaze residues, colorants, and additives used during the ceramic production process. Fired ceramic waste can be recovered and recycled in various ways. Common recycling methods include crushing and grinding ceramics to produce recycled aggregates for reuse in ceramic processes as well as in construction products like concrete.

D. The research team, composed of Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, UNITO) focused on bio-organic waste.

The Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW) is a biowaste produced in abundant quantities, yearly ranging around 180 Mt in Europe. OFMSW is generally landfilled, bringing negative effects to the environment. New methods of OFMSW managing and processing are thus being developed, with the aim of limiting its landfill disposal and converting it into high added value products.

Among biological treatments, anaerobic digestion is widely used because it produces digestate and biogas, allowing high energy recovery. Since digestate is rich in nutrients and low-degradable organic matter, it can be used as fertilizer. Additional research work is needed, to tune the nutrient balance in the digestate and optimize its efficiency in promoting plant growth and improving soil quality.

Possible reuses of the digestate coming from OFMSW have been reviewed also according to the European legislation and are depicted in the figure below.

Among these possible pathways our research will be directed on the recovery of nutrients (namely N and P) through the use of a controlled precipitation method.

The recovery of P from the liquid fraction of the digestate through chemical precipitation under controlled conditions (of various phosphate salts) is a consolidated technology on a pilot scale, while on a real scale still few plants are in operation in Europe, mostly waste water treatment plants and livestock. The most studied technology is the precipitation of struvite ($MgNH_4PO_4 \cdot H_2O$) and involves the addition of Mg to the liquid fraction to induce precipitation. Given the broad knowledge background present in Europe, struvite has been recently admitted in the European legislation (Regulation UE 2019/1009) together with biochar and ash-based products as an interesting product to be contained in fertilizer products. The precipitation of struvite depends on the characteristics of the matrix and the concentrations of the ions involved, for example on the molar ratio between ammonium and phosphate, on the concentration of Ca and Mg etc. For this reason, due to the greater variability of the characteristics of the OFMSW digestate compared to a vegetable or zootechnical digestate, and due to the lower concentration of P in an urban digestate compared to a waste water treatment plant, there are no definitive studies on the production of struvite from OFMSW.

E. The research team composed by Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Dept. of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Science, UNITO) and Chiara Milanese (Dept. of Chemistry, UNIPV) focuses on the equine stable bedding waste.

Equine stable bedding waste: Equines are generally housed in single box where the floor is covered by bedding. Dung and urine are mixed with the bedding material which commonly consist of rice husks,

straw, sawdust and wood shaving. It is estimated that one horse of around 500 kg bodyweight (BW) produces around 25 kg of waste per day (faeces plus urine). Since one horse kept in single box requires at least 10 kg of bedding material per day, combined bedding and manure accounts for up 12 tons (12,000 kg of wet waste per horse per year). The horse manure combined with the bedding material is actually an organic waste but represents a lignocellulosic material that has been recognised suitable for composting as well as for bioenergy recovery for heat and power generation: using the organic bedding materials as energy storage media (materials for solid state hydrogen storage and electrodes for electrochemical devices). Work is in progress to optimize the conversion procedures into biochar and activated carbon and to tune their surface morphology and composition to make the materials efficient for practical applications.

F. The research team composed by Claudio Forte, Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), focuses on agro-industrial wastes and their use in livestock. Marco Arlorio (UPO); focuses on agro-industrial wastes and their bio-based valorization using combined sustainable processing for the production of high value functional ingredients for food and nutraceuticals.

Agro-industrial wastes: It is estimated that agriculture generates around 700 million tons of waste annually in the European Union [1]. Most of the by-products derived from the agro-industry are actually treated as wastes, causing environmental issues and economic losses. Therefore, the recovery of processing wastes to be re-used in production processes represents a crucial challenge. According to the available scientific literature, some agro-industrial by-products, as the ones originating from hazelnuts, tubers and olives, are rich in bioactive compounds (Vitamins, polyphenols, antioxidants), and could be valorized by their inclusion in feed formulations for livestock.

Moreover, by-products from agri-food chains are largely reported in scientific literature as a potential source of high value compounds and ingredients for food and nutraceutical design [2]. According to the previously published scientific literature, cocoa bean hulls/shells (largely available, with a global estimated production of 700.000 tons/year), a waste generated during the roasting process of *Theobroma cacao* beans, can be considered a good source of antioxidant polyphenols, fibers and other bioactive compounds [3–5]. This matrix, even if deep chemically analysed as such, was not reported to be processed using combined bio-based and green methods. The use of enzyme-driven processing, fermentation, combined with ultrasounds and membrane ultrafiltration will be explored in order to select and set up a new performing method for cocoa beans shells valorisation, particularly focusing on functional prebiotic fibers with interesting rheological properties [6,7].

This holistic “bio-based and green” approach, will be also applied on other different matrices (fruit pomaces from apple, berries and more; by-products and wastes from legumes and vegetables; by products from grape and wine production) in order to investigate the best performing way to valorise them, as well as to recover functional ingredients for foods, nutraceutical, cosmeceutical and pharmaceutical applications [8–12]. More particularly, the fermentation using GRAS bacteria and fungi (e.g. lactobacilli and moulds used as starter cultures in food technology) will be achieved, applying all the information previously reported in literature, selecting the more performing combinations [13].

A peculiar focus (considering the previous data reported in literature) will be so focused on i) prebiotic fiber production, ii) bioactive polyphenols isolation and iii) bioactive peptides with nutraceutical properties (e.g. ACE-inhibition) [14–17].

G. The research team composed by Chiara Milanese (Dept. of Chemistry, UNIPV), Elena Savino, Simone Buratti and Carolina E. Girometta (Dept. of Earth and Environmental Sciences, UNIPV) focuses on the reuse of cereal and food waste for energy storage.

Food waste is defined as a decrease in food quality and quantity due from decisions and actions of retailers, food service suppliers and consumers (FAO, 2019). The main causes of food waste are the huge urbanization of the world population and the general food consumption behavior, which has led to an

increase in organic waste production no longer sustainable. The Food Waste Index Report 2021 estimates that food waste globally produces 931 million tons each year, of which 52% from households, 23% from food service and 23% from retail establishments (Food Waste Index Report, 2021). Moreover, the disposal of these by-products causes serious environmental hazards, due to the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) equal to around 3.3 billion tons of CO₂ per year accumulated in the atmosphere, contributing to impair climate emergency. In fact, common incineration of food waste increases air pollution by the production of dioxin, ash, and toxic gases as well as landfill disposal is one of the causes of groundwater contamination. Another crucial point is the economic effect of food wastage, which global cost amounts to 1000 billion dollars annually. This quantity is expected to increase up to 2600 billion dollars if environmental costs are ignored. Among commodities, vegetables firstly contribute to the economic cost of food loss and waste (23% of total cost), followed by meat (21%), fruits (19%), and cereals (18%) (FAO economic report, 2013).

All these wastes contain cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, bio-sources of carbon, considered a good candidate for energy storage if obtained in the suitable chemical and morphological form. In this research activity, food and agricultural wastes such as rice husk, bran and straw, corn stalk, melon and pumpkin peels, asparagus stems and bean pods are collected, washed and pyrolyzed under nitrogen atmosphere to obtain biochar. The pyrolysis time and temperature are under optimization to improve the chemical and morphological characteristics of the obtained materials depending on the final applications (chemical or electrochemical energy storage). Being the yield for biochar production still low (maximum 25%), the implementation of a biomass/vegetal waste pre-treatment process could result in a higher final yield. In this regard, fungi have been proposed for pretreatments of plant wastes to favour pyrolyzation process e.g. in wheat straw (Zhang et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022) and corn stover (Sun et al., 2022), besides true wood wastes (Rudakya et Gupte, 2017); significantly, wood decay fungi (WDF) are suggested in such pretreatments (Kan et al., 2016).

Fungi are major degraders in nature in a plethora of substrates, also including agro-industrial ones. Fungi are osmotrophic organisms and basically need to secrete lytic enzymes to decompose the substrate matrix and absorb nutrients (Deacon, 2005). With particular concern to plant wastes, they are able to attack all the components of plant cell wall in different tissues, organs and growth stages. Within the enormous diversity in Kingdom Fungi, the taxa involved in plant degradation are mainly included in Phyla Mucoromycota, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota, which have respectively evolved strategies to degrade increasingly recalcitrant substrates and polymers (Glass et al., 2013; Kubicek et al., 2014; Daniel, 2016). Since enzymatic degradation is also enhanced by physical penetration and disintegration by hyphae, filamentous fungi are usually preferred, respectively referring to Ascomycota moulds and Basidiomycota so-called macrofungi. The former usually show high competitiveness due to abundant vegetative reproduction (mainly by spores) and fast growth, whereas the latter usually display more complex enzymatic spectra addressing recalcitrant molecules. By the way, each species has optimal parameters to secrete different enzymes and can therefore shift the spectrum and strategy depending on the environmental conditions (Daniel, 2016).

The following macro-categories of enzymes should be mentioned with concern to plant wastes degradation (Andlar et al., 2018): pectinases, galacturonases, cellobiohydrolases, hemicellulases (e.g. xylanases), cellulases (acting on both crystalline and amorphous wastes of cellulose), cellobiose dehydrogenases, laccase and peroxidases (manganese, lignin, dye-degrading, white, etc.). The latter are especially involved in lignin degradation.

Wood decay fungi (WDF) are a major strategic asset of MicUNIPV, that is the research culture collection of the University of Pavia – Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences (Girometta et al., 2020; Cartabia et al., 2022). Few WDF strains in the collection have already been tested for degradation of

lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose in different agricultural wastes - namely rice straw, maize stalk and grape stalks. The pyrolysis process (investigated by thermogravimetric analysis, TGA) resulted in higher mass loss in plant wastes treated with mycelium in comparison to untreated wastes. Relative mass losses, as well as their primitive and derivative TGA profiles, are variable and depend on the fungal strain and the waste type, i.e. the cell wall component (lignin, hemicellulose, cellulose) that is most degraded by mycelium. Therefore, fungal pre-treatment of plant wastes may advantage the pyrolysis of recalcitrant compounds and improve the overall yield of the process.

Activation is also a critical parameter to obtain C materials porous enough to adsorb hydrogen or entrap ionic species in supercapacitors. KOH or CO₂ activation with different operative parameters are under optimization, too. The first promising results show that rice bran and melon peels allow to obtain superactivated C able to store more than 4 wt% H₂ in reversible way, while rice husk, richer in Si, is promising as electrode material for supercapacitor. Work is in progress to decorate the C surface with transition metals to catalyse the sorption reactions.

1.2 Syllabus Production (D1.1)

The literature research and analysis was followed by the development of a syllabus/database that has the aim of being a comprehensive repository of information designed to track and manage various types of waste generated throughout the production cycle. This database offers an overview of the state of the art of waste management, recovery, and sustainable practices by categorizing waste according to its type, its sector of origin within the production cycle, available alternatives for recovery, and the sector of the target production cycle.

The syllabus is organized as in the following:

Type of Waste: The database classifies waste into different categories based on their composition, characteristics, and source.

Sector of the Production Cycle of Origin: Each entry in the database includes information about the sector or stage in the production cycle where the waste originates. This could encompass a wide range of industries, such as manufacturing, agriculture, construction, healthcare, and more. Understanding the source of waste is crucial for implementing effective waste reduction and recycle strategies.

Alternative to disposal: The Waste Database provides insights into sustainable waste management by highlighting alternatives to traditional disposal methods. These alternatives may include recycling, composting, waste-to-energy conversion, or reusing materials.

Target sector for reintroducing resources: To promote circular economy practices, the database also identifies the sector or industry where the recovered materials or resources will be reintegrated. This facilitates the matching of waste streams with potential industrial partners, contributing to resource efficiency and reduced demand for new raw materials.

Two distinct versions of the syllabus have been developed.

The first is a comprehensive version you can find at this [link](#)

The second version is more simplified and you can find at this [link](#)

1.3. References

A. The research team led by Giovanna. A. Dino, Francesca Gambino, Manuela Lasagna, Domenico

Antonio De Luca and Sabrina Bonetto (Earth Sciences Department - UNITO)

Mine database literature [link](#)

Quarry database literature [link](#)

CDW-Excavation Waste: [link](#)

B. The research team, composed by Marco Bruno, Cesare Comina, Chiara Groppo, Anna Maria Ferrero, Stefano Ghignone, Andrea Giuliani, Franco Rolfo, Linda Pastero, Sergio Vinciguerra, Gessica Umili, and Dr Battista Taboni, focuses on the quarry and mining waste.

literature [Link](#)

C. The research team led by Prof. Mario Tribaudino and Dr. Andrea Bernasconi

literature [link](#)

D. The research team, composed of Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, UNITO) focused on bio-organic waste.

Literature [References biowaste.](#)

E. The research team composed by Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Dept. of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Science, UNITO) and Chiara Milanese (Dept. of Chemistry, UNIPV) focuses on the equine stable bedding waste.

Literature [Link.docx](#)

Literature [link](#)

F. The research team composed by Claudio Forte, Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), focuses on agro-industrial wastes and their use in livestock. Marco Arlorio (UPO); focuses on agro-industrial wastes and their bio-based valorization using combined sustainable processing for the production of high value functional ingredients for food and nutraceuticals.

Literature Unito [link](#)

Literature UPO [link](#)

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

The research team C led by Prof. Mario Tribaudino and Dr. Andrea Bernasconi (Earth Sciences Department, UNITO) acquired a gradient kiln (model Nannetti GR-20) to perform firing test at different temperatures up to 1300°C.

The research team A led by Giovanna Dino et al. (group from Earth Sciences Department, UNITO) acquired a magnetic separator.

The research team C, led by Elio Padoan (Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, UNITO) acquired instrumentation to determine nitrogen presence and form in organic and inorganic waste

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

In the next period the **research team A** leaded by Giovanna. A. Dino, Francesca Gambino, Manuela Lasagna, Domenico Antonio De Luca and Sabrina Bonetto (Earth Sciences Department - UNITO), Marco Casale (Management Department – UNITO), Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Dept. of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Science, UNITO), Giuseppina Cerrato and Alessia Giordana (Dept. of Chemistry, UNITO), Claudio Oggieri and Rossana Bellopede (DITAG – POLITO) focused on extractive waste (EW) and construction and demolition waste (CDW), will investigate, using different tools and instruments, the chance to characterize and recovery (for the objectives already presented at point 1) CDW and EW for the production of different products for environmental, civil, building, recreational applications.

In particular, the following activities will be carried out:

- at lab. scale:
 - a. Mineral processing of EW for CRM, RM, SRM concentration
 - b. Technosols for environmental purposes
 - c. Technosols and sublayers materials for horse footing areas
 - d. Testing and validation of mix design for restoring mortars
 - e. Mix design for CDW selected products for civil and infrastructure purposes
- at pilot site scale:
 - a. CDW selected products for civil and infrastructure purposes

- b. Technosols for environmental purposes
- c. Furthermore, environmental, social, economic and legislation issues connected to the application of tested new products and processing activities (at pilot scale and at real life scale) will be investigated (task 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4)

The **research team B** composed by Marco Bruno, Cesare Comina, Chiara Groppo, Anna Maria Ferrero, Stefano Ghignone, Andrea Giuliani, Franco Rolfo, Linda Pastero, Sergio Vinciguerra, Gessica Umili, and Dr Battista Taboni, (DST - UNITO), Maria Rita Migliazza, Maria Teresa Carriero (DISEG - POLITO), Federico Vagnon, Marilena Cardu (DIATI - POLITO) will work according to the following objectives:

- Mineralogical, petrographic, geophysical and geotechnical characterization of mine and quarry waste in a multiscale way, from micro to meso scale. In particular, two different lines of research will be carried out: one dedicated to carbonate and dolomitic rocks, the second one to ulexite-rich (Na- Ca- borate) rocks. - Development of experimental procedures specifically dedicated to the evaluation of the micro to macroscopic variations of rock materials subjected to environmental stress, to assess the possibility of using waste material from mines and quarries in the construction industry and in railway embarkment, in particular taking into account the environmental constraints.
- Development of theoretical and numerical constitutive models for hydro-chemo-mechanical stress-strain analysis of in situ application of the analyzed materials.
- analysis of procedures to increase the ore recovery and reduce waste during the production cycle. Moreover, the objective of Tailings Reduction is to develop a comprehensive strategy and establish clear outcomes for advancing progress towards cost-effective alternatives to conventionally managed tailings storage facilities. Key focus actions, such as technological advancements, operational best practices, environmental considerations, and regulatory frameworks can contribute to guide the implementation of the strategy and ensure a correct approach to tailings reduction.

The **research team C** led by Prof. Mario Tribaudino and Dr. Andrea Bernasconi (Dip. Scienze della Terra, UNITO) foresees the following objectives:

- _ characterization of thermally treated (up to about 1250°C) MSW-bottom ashes by X-ray Powder Diffraction, X-ray Fluorescence, Scanning Electron Microscopy and leaching test;
- _ evaluation of the introduction of MSW-bottom ashes in the ceramic process by combination of both technological and mineralogical approaches (X-ray Powder Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscopy and leaching test);
- _ evaluation of the introduction of fired ceramic waste in the ceramic process by combination of both technological and mineralogical approaches (X-ray Powder Diffraction and Scanning Electron Microscopy).

The **research team D**, led by Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, UNITO) will aim to achieve the following objectives at lab scale:

- Characterization of:

- a. Organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW)
 - b. Digestate produced by OFMSW anaerobic digestion
 - c. Liquid fraction of the OFMSW digestate
- Optimization of a method for controlled struvite precipitation from the liquid fraction of the OFMSW digestate to recover phosphorous and nitrogen.
 - Evaluation of enzymatic pretreatments to be applied on the OFMSW, with the aim of promoting organic matter degradation and phosphorous solubilization, thus increasing the biogas production during the anaerobic digestion and improving the precipitated struvite quality and quantity.
 - Characterization of the struvite and the digestate liquid fraction after struvite removal, to select the most promising pretreatment method.

The **research team E** led by Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO), Elio Padoan and Alice Boarino (Dept. of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Science, UNITO) and Chiara Milanese (Dept. of Chemistry, UNIPV) expects to develop the following steps:

- to characterize several organic bedding materials (dung and urine mixed with rice husks, or straw, or sawdust) in terms of pH, concentration of ammonia and nitrates, total carbon, total nitrogen, carbonates and metal contents (Fe, Mn, Cd, Cr, Cu, Co, Ni, Pb and Zn)
- to explore the use of organic bedding materials from equine stables as energy storage media (materials for solid state hydrogen storage and electrodes for electrochemical devices)
- to optimise the conversion procedures into biochar and activated carbon
- to develop prototype to use on field condition

The **research team F** composed by Claudio Forte, Emanuela Valle, Federica Raspa and Clara Bordin (Dept. of Veterinary Sciences, UNITO) expect to develop the following steps:

- to characterise the selected agro-industrial by-products in terms of proximate analysis, bioactive compounds (vitamins, polyphenols, antioxidants) and *in-vitro* microbial activity.
- to include agro-industrial by-products in feedstuffs for different animal species (cattle and poultry) and plan diets to satisfy the nutritional requirements of animals.
- to carry out *in vivo* trials to evaluate the effects of the inclusion of the selected agro-industrial by-products in feedstuff on: (i) animal health (evaluation of emato-biochemical profile, oxidative status and welfare parameters) and (ii) animal productions in terms of growth performances.
- to evaluate *post-mortem* meat quality traits (in terms of nutritional value and bioactive compounds), meat safety and meat shelf life.
- to assess the consumers' acceptance.

The **research team G** composed by Chiara Milanese (Dept. of Chemistry, UNIPV), Elena Savino, Simone Buratti and Carolina E. Girometta (Dept. of Earth and Environmental Sciences, UNIPV)

will work according to the following objectives:

- set up and optimization of the fungal pre-treatment of the different plant wastes depending on their composition in organic components;
- optimization of the pyrolysis conditions for the different wastes and verification of the effect of fungi on the yields of the decomposition processes and on the porosity improvements of the materials;
- set up and optimization of the procedures of decoration with metals and metal oxides for the activated C based materials' surfaces to catalyze the sorption reactions. Innovative techniques for the preparation of nanoparticles such as spray pyrolysis will be tested.